

Experimental and Theoretical Studies of Injection Moulding
Considering the Unstable Flow Behaviour
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ABSTRACT

The ununiform progress of the flow front during an injection moulding is investigated on a cup-shaped FRTP component in this paper. The ununiform flow behaviour influences upon the orientation of the reinforcement in FRTP products, strongly.

This projecting part is assumed here to be caused by the unstable flow behaviour under the kinetic condition, not to be caused by the unexpected mould condition. Therefore, the experiment is compared with the analysis taking the unstable flow state into consideration.

The experimental results are well explained by this analytical results. Moreover, on the orientation of the reinforcement, the numerical results after this flow analysis show to be in good agreement with the experiment.

KEYWORDS: Injection moulding, FRTP, Unstable flow behaviour,
Finite element analysis, Short-shot process

1. INTRODUCTION

Injection moulding used in various industrial fields is recently applied to the moulding of FRTP. The injection moulding of FRTP is replacing other materials or methods because of the productivity of the process and the quality of the

products, particularly specific strength and specific stiffness.

In injection moulding, though Computer Aided Design system is widely applied, most of these system are constructed for the flow analysis of resin using hele-show model or similar model. And these system without the consideration of the viscosity in plane can not exactly obtain the orientation of the reinforcement.

We have been constructing the CAD system for FRTP injection moulding, a series of the flow analysis considering the viscosity in plane and thickness direction, the fibre orientation analysis and the warp and stress analysis. Our system is in good agreement with experiment, mainly. But partly, the confused orientation of the reinforcement was found out in experimental results. In the short-shot injection moulding used in our flow front analysis, the ununiform progresses of the flow front were observed. This material behaviour seemed to influence upon the confused orientation of the reinforcement. By the previous system, these behaviour making a projecting part could not be estimated.

In this paper, the purpose in the experiments is made clear to arise the ununiform flow behaviour of melt resin in a cavity. So, the shapes of the flow front are observed by the short-shot process of cup-shaped component.

In the numerical analysis, the idealised model using eigenvalue analysis considering unstable flow behaviour are applied to the flow behaviour with the ununiformity of the flow front progress. The flow analysis which was used in our previous study is carried out adding the above model. The numerical results using the eigenvalue analysis are compared with experiments.

2. EXPERIMENTS

To understand the ununiform flow behaviour of melt resin during injection moulding, the projection of the flow front is observed in each the short-shot mouldings, because of the invisibility in a cavity. The short-shot moulding means a lack of the injection shot volume for a cavity. Experiments were carried out on cup-shaped component using the injection moulding machine, as shown in Fig.1. Materials are polypropylene and

glass fibre reinforced polypropylene (respectively TOKUYAMA SODA Co.,LTD. ME150 and GS255), which are crystalline plastics, and ABS resin and glass fibre reinforced ABS resin (respectively DAICEL CHEMICAL INDUSTRIES,LTD. V510 and VGR20) which are amorphous plastics.

The projection of the flow front of the short-shot mouldings is measured by the equipment shown in Fig.2. This measuring system has 76 measurement points per one revolution using a laser displacement gauge. On measurement of side part, the laser displacement gauge is parallel to the axis.

Fibre orientation is observed using soft X-ray photography. Carbon fibres electroplated in copper, which are visible under X-ray radiation, are used as tracer fibres.

Fig.1 Shape and dimensions of the specimen.

Fig.2 Block diagram of deflection measurement system.

The shape of the flow front in the disk part is observed the projecting part in a few directions as shown in Fig.3(a) and (b). In the side part, the state of projecting part is similar to that in the disk part as shown in Fig.4. It is seemed that

the number of the projecting parts of crystalline plastics is more than that of amorphous plastics, and this tendency is stronger in glass fibre reinforced plastics.

The direction of the projecting part is checked up. And it is observed that the projecting part occurs in random direction as shown in Fig.5. Therefore the ununiform progress of the flow front is seemed to be occurred by the unstable flow behaviour depending on the kinetic condition of melt resin during injection moulding, not by the unexpected mould condition such as a temperature distribution, a error in thickness of a cavity and other experimental error condition.

Fig.3 Experimental results about shape of flow front in the disk part.

Fig.4 Experimental results about shape of flow front in the side part.
(P.P. ; Glass fiber content = 0 wt%)

Fig.5 Probable flow direction of flow front in the disk part.
(P.P. ; Glass fiber content = 0 wt%)

The fibre orientation is shown in Fig.6. The lines shown in the diagram are drawn so that the direction gives the mean fibre orientation and the length shows the orientation factor. The state of the fibre orientation in the disk part shows a concentric circles, and in side part shows a parallel orientation to circumference.

Fig.6 Diagram of the tracer fiber orientation.
(P.P. ; Glass fiber content = 0 wt%)

3. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

To consider results of experiments, the unstable flow behaviour is assumed to arise during injection moulding. In the numerical analysis using finite element method, the modelling of the mechanical behaviour during process is achieved as follows (see Fig.7). For the first step, the deformation state does not depend on the injection rate, but is governed by the eigen mode of deformation. Thus an estimate of the deformation state before the initiation of flow is calculated by eigenvalue analysis.

The second mode should be used to investigate the subsequent process, because the energy level of the second mode is lower than the next. The first mode means the rigid rotation. The result is then applied to the following step. The sequence of deformation is then simulated by linear incremental analysis, as an infinitesimal deformation due to sprue pressure. The strain rate is determined and the initial viscosity can be estimated. The analysis for the flow process is then applied.

Fig.7 Flow chart for numerical procedure.

Examples of the results of velocity vectors and pressure distribution are shown in Fig.8(a) and (b) respectively, which are for isotropic materials. The disturbed flow state, for an example in the circle, is obtained in Fig.8(a) and isobaric lines are not circular in the disk part and not straight in the side part as shown in Fig.8(b). Filling-up processes obtained by the flow analysis are shown in Fig.9. They showed the asymmetrical flow front shapes resulting in the ununiform progress of the flow front. After eigenvalue analysis, it is certified that the unstable flow behaviour is estimated by flow analysis. The shapes of flow front in anisotropic materials analysis are more unstable than in isotropic materials. These results are in good agreement with the experiments.

An example of the fibre orientation analysis is shown in Fig.10 to compare with the experiment (shown in Fig.6.). It is found that the result of the fibre orientation analysis agrees with the result of the experiments.

4. DISCUSSION

The results of experiments show the ununiform flow behaviours in short-shot moulding. In general, crystalline plastics has stronger anisotropy than amorphous plastics. And the anisotropy is increased with the reinforcement. As anisotropy

Fig.8 Results of flow analysis. (Time = 0.03743 sec.)

Fig.9 Filling-up process on filling element obtained by flow analysis.

Fig.10 Fiber orientation obtained by numerical analysis.
(Time = 0.03601 sec.)

in the crystalline resin or glass fibre reinforced plastics is stronger the instability of flow front is increased. Consideration of the instability is needed for a design of precision moulding.

As the results of this analysis are compared with the experiments, it is shown that the model of this eigenvalue analysis is available. An anisotropy must be considered in crystalline materials and fibre orientation analysis.

5. CONCLUSION

Consequently, the following conclusions are obtained.

- (1) The unstable behaviour in melt resin during injection moulding process is observed in the shape of flow front on short-shot moulding, not caused by the unexpected mould condition.
- (2) The numerical analysis developed by considering eigenvalue analysis in this paper is able to simulate the ununiform progress of the flow front during injection moulding process. The flow state of the crystalline resin shows the stronger irregularity than that of the amorphous resin. And the flow state of stronger anisotropic material shows the stronger irregularity.
- (3) The fibre orientation analysis after the flow analysis with

eigenvalue analysis shows to be in good agreement with experiments. The fibre orientation depending upon the unstable flow shows partly confused orientation similar to experimental result.

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